

Tropic of Diabetes: A Mathematical Modelling for precision in position(location).

Arjun Dahal

Mental Asylum of Education

P.O. Box 1,

Gauradaha, Jhapa

[Orcid ID: https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7796-7971](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7796-7971)

Abstract:

Our study of maps, based on Greenwich Meridian line, tropic of cancer, tropic of capricorn, arctic circle, antartic circle, line of equator; allows us to study about places and locations, based on geographical description, as per latitudes, and longitudes. In this paper, we have introduced Mathematical co-ordinates, and co-ordinate geometry, to obtain precision in location.

Keywords: Maps, Navigation, GPS, Tropic of Diabetes, Earth, Mathematical Geography.

Introduction:

Let us consider a map as a rectangular diagram as per our present-day understanding.

[1]

Since our Greenwich Meridian Line, and Line of Equator are considered as $(0,0)$, we shall introduce cartesian co-ordinates, by making Greenwich Meridian line as Y-axis, and line of equator as X-axis.

That would make our figure look like as

Introducing cartesian co-ordinates would allow us to define some point $O(0,0)$, based on geometrical description of earth, by means geometry, any point $P(x,y)$ on cartesian plane can be treated by means of mathematics, still preserving the functionality of latitudes and longitudes and entire geographical description.

When our earth, or any object is considered as per their geometry; for an example, when earth is considered as a sphere, then we can draw three dimensional cartesian co-ordinates as shown in figure below.

This figure, then does allows us to study about geography, as well as Mathematics, to discuss about position, as well as location with greater accuracy.

We shall begin from simplest example in mathematics, that for any two points $P(x_1, y_1)$ and $Q(x_2, y_2)$, distance between them is given by,

$$S = \sqrt{(x_2 - x_1)^2 + (y_2 - y_1)^2}$$

which is our famous distance formula in co-ordinate geometry.

Thus we can introduce entire co-ordinate geometry and mathematics, to define any position, with greater accuracy, where as location as per latitudes and longitudes would have no effect, and wouldn't be effected at all, which would allow us to study geography too.

Transformation of co-ordinates would further allow us to study based on our preference for co-ordinate systems like as Curvilinear co-ordinate system, and Polar co-ordinate system.

Furthermore, when we provide any location based on streets, places, house numbers, block numbers, and other parameters, then again standarization of address would be achieved with precision, where as Mathematical tools would bring convinicy and ease in calculations, as well as GPS system too would be improvised.

Conclusion and Need:

For better Mathematical modelling, developing a software would be better, so that, we can have precision in location and address system, for mobile use, as well as for study purposes.

Actknowledgement:

The term "Tropic of Diabetes" did emerged as a fun during talks, when one of our friend Ashin Singh Mahat questioned, Why isn't there tropic of diabetes, but just tropic of cancer, and tropic of capricorn. Thus, more then non-communicable disease, we shall discuss our topics as "Tropic of Diabetes Model", for achieving precision in finding any location, based on point, allowing us for providing treatment, as needed, being uneffected by geographical parameters, like latitudes and longitudes, yet still introducing Mathematical Geography. Author hasn't prepared diagrams in computarized form, which is lack of knowledge in mathematical tools in computing and essentially lazyness of author as well.

References:

1. <https://www.angelo.edu/faculty/mdixon/ManEnvironment/climate4.htm> Last accessed on 21 August 2021.
2. Arjun Dahal. (2021). On Standarization of Addresses. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4904541>, Vixra:[2106.0018]